

The motivation behind multiplying Z by $10^n + 1$ was that the addition of zeros and a 1 would enable any probable prime P to be easily provable if at least 33% of $P - 1$ could be factored. In other words, we hoped to give $P - 1$ enough 2s and 5s to make it easily provable. Yet the first three values found: 300, 307, 313, did not allow $Z * 10^n$ to have enough small factors and so they had to be certified with the online ECM factorization applet written by Dario Alpern[5]. The other two primes were easily provable since more than 33% of $P - 1$ could be factored.

Conjecture: There are infinitely many Smarandache car primes.

Questions: What other “concrete” numerical figures can be designed that simultaneously have mathematical properties? Can any squares, perfect powers, or Niven numbers be found that display “pictures” of any kind in their digits?

References

1. Smarandache Sequences, Vol. I,
<http://www.gallup.unm.edu/~smarandache/SNAQINT.txt>
2. Wikipedia, “Concrete Poetry,”
http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Concrete_poetry
3. RPO, George Herbert, “Easter Wings”,
<http://eir.library.utoronto.ca/rpo/display/poem973.html>
4. PrimeFormGW (PFGW), Primality-Testing Program Discussion Group,
<http://groups.yahoo.com/group/primeform/>
5. Dario Alpern, Factorization Using the Elliptic Curve Method Applet,
<http://www.alpertron.com.ar/ECM.HTM>

-end-

Jason Earls is author of the books *Red Zen*, *How to Become a Guitar Player from Hell*, *Heartless Bastard In Ecstasy*, *Cocoon of Terror*, `If(Sid_Vicious == TRUE && Alan_Turing == TRUE)` `{ERROR_Cyberpunk(); }` and 0.136101521283645567... available at Amazon.com and other online book stores.

His fiction and mathematical work have been published in Red Scream, Scientia Magna, Wretched & Violent, Mathworld, Chiaroscuro, three of Clifford Pickover’s books, Switchblade, Dogmatika, Neometropolis, Prime Curios, the Online Encyclopedia of Integer Sequences, OG’s Speculative Fiction, AlienSkin, Escaping Elsewhere, Werewolf, Recreational and Educational Computing, Thirteen, Theatre of Decay, Nocturnal Ooze, Prime Curios, Bust Down the Door and Eat All the Chickens, Swallow’s Tail, and

other publications. He currently resides in Texas with his wife, Christine.